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Innovative Cognitive Tools for Studying Market Opportunities for Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of cognitive technologies into business processes sets new requirements for market opportunity analytics, and digital analytics makes it possible to accurately measure its impact on business models and innovative solutions. The aim of the study is to quantify the role of cognitive tools in the dynamics of entrepreneurial opportunities, identify factors that change this correlation, and build a panel model. The methodological foundation